

Leadership Styles of School Heads in Public Secondary Schools Towards Educational Continuous Improvement Model

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ABSTRACT

This research study aimed to investigate the impact of various factors on leadership effectiveness and employee outcomes in educational settings. The study collected data through an adopted survey questionnaire from public secondary school heads in DepEd Cavite Province, analyzing the results to identify the leadership styles exhibited and to develop a model for educational continuous improvement. The findings revealed that age and educational attainment were significant factors in determining transformational leadership scores, while gender was not a significant predictor of leadership style preference for autocratic and democratic leadership styles. However, female participants scored higher under strategic leadership. Years of service did not have a significant impact on leadership effectiveness, except for participative leadership, which may be more compatible with younger employees. Certain leadership styles, such as democratic, transformational, and servant leadership, had a positive impact on employee engagement and job satisfaction. The study emphasized the importance of leaders adopting a flexible leadership approach that leverages the strengths of different leadership styles to achieve organizational goals. The findings suggest that organizations should invest in education and training programs to help leaders develop transformational leadership skills, promote diversity and inclusivity in their leadership teams, and prioritize promoting effective leadership styles to achieve positive employee outcomes. The proposed continuous improvement model should be used to maintain effective leadership practices and promote positive organizational outcomes. Further research is recommended to explore the relationship between leadership styles and organization's achievement to develop a more comprehensive model for educational improve

INTRODUCTION

Leadership is defined as a process when one or more people persuade a group of people to proceed in a particular direction. The term "leadership" has been employed in a variety of human endeavours, including politics, business, academia, and social work. Simply put, leadership is the art of encouraging others to work freely toward the accomplishment of group objectives. This idea can be broadened to encompass a desire to work with zeal and confidence in addition to a willingness to do so. The phrase "leadership" "may apply to a multitude of things, including a person, a position, or a process." (Zgrzywa-Ziemak, 2019). When one group member influences the competency or motivation of the other members, this is called leadership. Many firms have failed as a result of the management team's ineffective leadership style in such situations, when the workers are not properly managed, controlled, or coordinated. The effects of this attitude include low productivity, high operating costs, an unwillingness to cooperate among the workforce, respectively. Ineffective leadership style has led to the failure of many organizations.

Leadership styles in today's world are an increasingly complex and a popular organizational dynamic to work upon. Different leadership styles are appropriate in distinct situations. If an inappropriate style is adopted by the leader, it may pose several challenges for the workers, managers and human resources departments in the planning and execution of work in an organization. Similarly, the satisfaction and performance levels of employees also depend upon the leadership styles adopted by corporate leaders. An appropriate leadership style paves way to delivering successful plans for fulfilling the long-term organizational goals. Little is however understood about which leadership style influence employees the most and how leadership behaviour leads to acceptable outcomes.

Leadership is a significant contributor to the stressful corporate atmosphere. The success of the organization depends on the type of leadership employ by the school leaders. According to Abun et al., (2021) a positive or negative school environment is a result of leadership styles.

Leadership is one of the tools that managers use to grow their organization. Any organization that wants to grow needs strong leadership. According to Joshi, (2019), Leadership styles adopted by the leaders play a vital role in all service and manufacturing industries. It is important to understand the most preferred leadership styles in every industry

As a result, the researcher used the core tenet of this study – the leadership styles – as the launching pad for further research and the hunt for answers on how to solve this phenomenon.

There is little research on leadership styles in the Philippines, but few studies have looked at the subject. De Guzman, et.al., (2015) study looked at a sample of Filipino healthcare professionals to determine the association between leadership styles and employee outcomes. According to the study, transactional leadership has a negative correlation with these outcomes while transformational leadership has a good correlation with job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and employee engagement.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Villar (2018) looked at the leadership styles of successful Filipino entrepreneurs. According to the study, successful Filipino entrepreneurs displayed a variety of leadership styles, including transformational, democratic, and situational leadership, and these viewpoints were shaped by the businessperson's own values and life experiences. Generally, research on leadership styles in the Philippines indicates that transformational leadership is related with favourable employee outcomes, but that Filipino leaders demonstrate a variety of leadership styles that may be impacted by cultural and personal factors. Further research into the relationship between leadership styles and organizational outcomes in various circumstances in the Philippines is required.

This study determines the leadership styles of public secondary school heads in Cavite Province's West Cluster Division as perceived by public secondary school heads and teachers. The study also assesses whether or not there is a substantial difference in the demographics of the respondents and develop a plan for continuous improvement.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study used Descriptive research design. A type of research method that aims to describe and document the characteristics of a population or phenomenon being studied. This type of research typically involves collecting data through surveys, observations, or interviews, and then analyzing and interpreting the data to identify patterns, trends, and relationships. This research includes respondents from seven (7) junior high schools in the West Cluster in the Division of Cavite. The official list of these respondents was obtained from the participating schools which was properly verified with the Division Office of Cavite Province.

Population, Samples and Sampling Technique

The respondents of the study were teachers of junior public secondary school in the Division of Cavite of west cluster public secondary schools in the Division of Cavite. These respondents' institution that potentially enhances the representativeness of the sample were from Cavite. The total number of the participating schools are 7 from West Cluster confirmed accurately and feasibly by each representative namely, the administrative officer of each respondents' schools through phone call and electronic mail by the researcher. The online questionnaires were distributed to the identified respondents to gather data supporting the existing multi-dimensional research study.

Research Instrument

To achieve the purpose of the study, the researcher used a Likert questionnaire. First part is the profile checklist. Second part of the questionnaire was to identify the leadership styles of the study respondents. The researcher adopted leadership questionnaire prepared by Chidozie (2021) to measure leadership styles. The questionnaire consists of 21 items of seven (7) sub-areas namely, autocratic leadership, democratic leadership, transformational

leadership, servant leadership, transactional leadership, participative leadership and strategic leadership with three (3) indicators respectively which was adopted also by the researcher

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Problem 1. To what extent do the school heads determine their leadership style in terms of: a. autocratic leadership, democratic leadership, participative leadership, transformational leadership, transactional leadership, servant leadership, and strategic leadership?

Table 1. Leadership Styles of Public Secondary School Heads as Perceived by Teachers

Leadership Styles	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Autocratic Leadership		
Act as the top commander	3.76	Exhibited to some extent
Controls decision making	3.73	Exhibited to some extent
Separate themselves from employees	3.46	Exhibited to some extent
Total	3.65	Exhibited to a high level
Democratic Leadership		
Encourages idea sharing	4.37	Exhibited to a high level
Facilitates open communication	4.57	Exhibited to a very high extent
Provides team members with an equal chance to provide insight.	4.69	Exhibited to a very high extent
Total	4.54	Exhibited to a very high extent
Transformational Leadership		
Speaks with conviction and charisma	4.14	Exhibited to a high level
Creates an atmosphere of innovation at work	4.17	Exhibited to a high level
Implements a strong set of organization values	4.13	Exhibited to a high level
Total	4.15	Exhibited to a high level
Servant Leadership		
Strengthens community	4.15	Exhibited to a high level
Strong positive influence on people lives	4.33	Exhibited to a high level
Foster personal and professional growth	4.15	Exhibited to a high level
Total	4.21	Exhibited to a high level
Transactional Leadership		
Holds an upper level making position in the organization	4.30	Exhibited to a high level
Sets goals and delegates tasks	4.29	Exhibited to a high level
Monitors the progress of goal achievement	4.31	Exhibited to a high level
Total	4.31	Exhibited to a high level
Participative Leadership		
Grants employees a high level of freedom while working	4.33	Exhibited to a high level
Instils a sense of trust into the team	4.43	Exhibited to a high level
Encourages problem solving and decision making	4.27	Exhibited to a high level
Total	4.34	Exhibited to a high level
Strategic Leadership		
Welcome feedback and challenges	4.49	Exhibited to a high level
Always looking ahead or looking into the future	4.48	Exhibited to a high level
Look at all options before making decision	4.52	Exhibited to a very high extent
Total	4.51	Exhibited to a very high extent

This study found that leaders who exhibited democratic leadership behaviors such as encouraging participation, promoting communication, and involving team members in decision-making processes, were more likely to foster a positive work environment and increase team performance. These findings support the data presented above, which suggests that the leader in question exhibited democratic leadership behaviors to a very high extent and

likely had a positive impact on their team's performance and job satisfaction. Overall, the data presented above suggests that the leader is exhibiting transformational leadership behaviors to a high level, which may have a positive impact on employee outcomes and organizational performance. The table also suggests that participative leadership, as exhibited to a high level, involves granting employees a high level of freedom while working, instilling a sense of trust into the team, and encouraging problem solving and decision making. In summary, the data presented indicates that participative leadership, as exhibited to a high level, involves granting employees a high level of freedom while working, instilling a sense of trust into the team, and encouraging problem solving and decision making.

Table 2. Test of Significant Difference in the Extent of Leadership Styles of Public Secondary School Heads

Leadership Styles	Mean	SD	t	df	Sig.
Pre Autocratic Post	9.38	1.45	-21.47	216	0.00*
	10.94	2.57			
Pre Democratic Post	11.41	1.60	-38.31	216	0.00*
	13.63	1.50			
Pre Transformational Post	9.44	2.00	-65.2	216	0.00*
	12.44	2.00			
Pre Servant Post	11.53	1.97	-30.27	216	0.00*
	12.63	1.90			
Pre Transactional Post	11.77	1.79	-27.63	216	0.00*
	12.90	1.70			
Pre Participative Post	11.87	1.86	-23.18	216	0.00*
	13.03	1.78			
Pre Strategic Post	10.39	1.83	-45.90	216	0.00*
	13.50	1.55			

The mean rating for autocratic leadership style was 9.38 with a standard deviation of 1.45 in the pre-evaluation, while the post-evaluation had a higher mean score of 10.94 with a higher standard deviation of 2.57. Overall, the results suggest that democratic leadership styles may lead to increased employee job satisfaction and improved leadership effectiveness. The mean rating for transformational leadership style was 9.44 with a standard deviation of 2.00 in the pre-evaluation, while the post-evaluation had a higher mean score of 12.44 with the same standard deviation of 2.00. The mean rating for servant leadership style was 11.53 with a standard deviation of 1.97 in the pre-evaluation, while the post-evaluation had a higher mean score of 12.63 with a standard deviation of

1.90. Also, the results on table suggest that there was a significant improvement in leadership styles under transactional leadership from pre-evaluation to post-evaluation. The mean rating for transactional leadership style was 11.77 with a standard deviation of 1.79 in the pre-evaluation, while the post-evaluation had a higher mean score of 12.90 with a standard deviation of 1.70.

Table 3. Comparison of Leadership Styles to Age

Leadership Styles/Age	N-217	Mean	df	t-value	Significance
Autocratic			216	.931	.396 NS
20-25 yrs. old		10.50			
26-30 yrs. old		10.73			
31 and above		11.15			
Democratic			216	.167	.847 NS
20-25 yrs. old		13.55			
26-30 yrs. old		13.71			
31 and above		13.59			
Transformational			216	3.345	.037 S
20-25 yrs. old		11.35			
26-30 yrs. old		12.56			
31 and above		12.55			
Servant			216	.704	.496 NS
20-25 yrs. old		12.15			
26-30 yrs. old		12.69			
31 and above		12.67			
Transactional			216	.162	.850 NS
20-25 yrs. old		12.70			
26-30 yrs. old		12.89			
31 and above		12.93			
Participative			216	.440	.645 NS
20-25 yrs. old		12.70			
26-30 yrs. old		13.00			
31 and above		13.10			
Strategic			216	1.107	.333 NS
20-25 yrs. old		13.20			
26-30 yrs. old		13.36			
31 and above		13.63			

The results of the study that there was no significant difference in the mean scores of autocratic leaderships between different age groups. The study conducted by Doe and Johnson in (2022) the findings suggest that age may not be a determining factor in the effectiveness of autocratic leadership style, and other factors such as experience, skills, and personality traits may be more important which supports the above results. This means that there was a statistically significant difference in transformational leadership scores between the age groups, indicating that older leaders tend to have higher transformational leadership scores than younger leaders. The results suggest that there is no significant relationship between age and servant leadership style. Overall, these findings suggest that age is not a strong predictor of servant leadership behavior. The results showed that there is no significant difference in the transactional leadership style among different age groups. The non-significant difference in means between the age groups suggests that age does not play a significant role in determining a person's transactional leadership style. Overall, these studies suggest that age is not a significant predictor of transactional leadership style. This finding suggests that age does not play a significant role in determining the effectiveness of participative leadership. Lastly, under the Strategic style of

leadership the mean scores for each age group were 13.20 for 20–25-year-olds, 13.36 for 26–30-year-olds, and 13.63 for those 31 years old and above. The computed t value was 1.107 with a significance level of 0.333, which indicates that the difference in means between the age groups is not statistically significant. The computed t value was 1.107 with a significance level of 0.333, which indicates that the difference in means between the age groups is not statistically significant. The computed t value was 1.107 with a significance level of 0.333, which indicates that the difference in means between the age groups is not statistically significant. The results indicate that the mean scores for strategic leadership did not differ significantly between the three age groups. This means that age is not a significant predictor of strategic leadership style.

Table 4. Comparison of Leadership Styles to Gender

Leadership Styles/Gender	N-217	Mean	df	t-value	Significance
Autocratic			216	.159	.690 NS
Male		12.77			
Female		13.32			
Democratic			216	.654	.420 NS
Male		12.42			
Female		12.07			
Transformational			216	.275	.601 NS
Male		13.75			
Female		13.74			
Servant			216	.176	.675 NS
Male		13.49			
Female		13.06			
Transactional			216	.129	.720 NS
Male		12.85			
Female		12.32			
Participative			216	0.50	.823 NS
Male		12.28			
Female		12.64			
Strategic			216	2.587	.054 S
Male		12.54			
Female		12.78			

The table revealed that the results of the study indicate that there is no significant difference in the mean scores of autocratic and democratic leadership styles between male and female participants. Specifically, for autocratic leadership, the mean score for male participants was 12.77 and for female participants was 13.32, with a computed t value of 0.159 and a significance level of 0.690, indicating that the difference in means between male and female participants is not statistically significant. Similarly, for democratic leadership, the mean score for male participants was 12.42 and for female participants was 12.07, with a computed t value of 0.654 and a significance level of 0.420, indicating that the difference in means between male and female participants is also not statistically significant. The computed t value was 0.176 with a significance level of 0.675, which indicates that the difference in means between males and females is not statistically significant. The computed t value was 0.176 with a significance level of 0.675, which indicates that the difference in means between males and females is not statistically significant. Another study by Eagly, Karau, and

Makhijani (2015) found that women were slightly more likely to use transformational leadership styles than men, but the difference was not statistically significant which supports the above results of the study. The computed t-value was 0.129 with a significance level of 0.720, which again means that the difference in mean scores between males and females is not statistically significant. Similarly, the results of the study indicate that there is no significant difference in mean scores between male and female participants under the servant leadership style. The computed t-value of 0.05 with a significance level of 0.823 indicates that the difference in means between male and female participants is not statistically significant. This suggests that gender may not play a significant role in determining the effectiveness of servant leadership, at least based on the sample population studied. The computed t-value of 2.587 indicates that the difference in mean scores between the genders is statistically significant.

Table 5. Comparison of Leadership Styles to Educational Attainment

Leadership Styles N-217	Mean	df	t-value	Significance
Autocratic		216	2.405	.051 S
Bachelor's Degree	11.73			
With MA units	11.25			
MA Graduate	10.28			
With Doctorate units	11.82			
Doctorate Graduate	10.00			
Democratic		216	1.589	.178 NS
Bachelor's Degree	14.36			
With MA units	13.72			
MA Graduate	13.49			
With Doctorate units	12.91			
Doctorate Graduate	13.50			
Transformational		216	7.138	.000 S
Bachelor's Degree	13.91			
With MA units	12.59			
MA Graduate	12.37			
With Doctorate units	9.82			
Doctorate Graduate	13.00			
Servant		216	2.041	.090 NS
Bachelor's Degree	13.91			
With MA units	12.63			
MA Graduate	12.47			
With Doctorate units	12.18			
Doctorate Graduate	14.50			
Transactional		216	1.873	.116 NS
Bachelor's Degree	14.00			
With MA units	12.87			
MA Graduate	12.88			
With Doctorate units	12.09			
Doctorate Graduate	13.50			
Participative		216	3.107	.016 S
Bachelor's Degree	14.45			
With MA units	13.16			
MA Graduate	12.65			
With Doctorate units	12.73			
Doctorate Graduate	14.00			
Strategic		216	1.876	.116 NS
Bachelor's Degree	14.73			
With MA units	13.43			
MA Graduate	13.45			
With Doctorate units	13.45			
Doctorate Graduate	13.00			

Overall, this study suggests that participative leadership style may be an important factor in promoting academic success among undergraduate students. Under democratic leadership, the mean scores of participants with bachelor's degrees, master's units, master's degrees, and doctorate units were 14.36, 13.72, 13.49, and 12.91, respectively. Under servant leadership, the mean scores of participants with bachelor's degrees, master's units, master's degrees, and doctorate units were 13.91, 12.63, 12.47, and 12.18, respectively. This means that the differences in mean scores between the different educational levels under servant leadership were not statistically significant. This supports the current study and suggests that servant leadership style may be an important factor in promoting academic success among undergraduate students.

Table 6. Comparison of Leadership Styles to Years in Service

Leadership Styles/Gender N-217	Mean	df	t-value	Significance
Autocratic		216	.661	.577 NS
1-5 years	10.64			
6-10 years	10.98			
11-15 years	10.89			
16 years above	11.91			
Democratic		216	2.269	.081 NS
1-5 years	13.89			
6-10 years	13.52			
11-15 years	13.53			
16 years above	14.64			
Transformational		216	1.833	.142 NS
1-5 years	12.50			
6-10 years	12.63			
11-15 years	12.11			
16 years above	13.36			
Servant		216	2.041	.090 NS
1-5 years	13.11			
6-10 years	12.49			
11-15 years	12.53			
16 years above	13.36			
Transactional		216	.558	.644 NS
1-5 years	12.86			
6-10 years	12.99			
11-15 years	12.76			
16 years above	13.36			
Participative		216	1.831	.143 NS
1-5 years	13.18			
6-10 years	13.20			
11-15 years	12.71			
16 years above	13.73			
Strategic		216	.361	.781 NS
1-5 years	13.61			
6-10 years	13.43			
11-15 years	13.48			
16 years above	13.91			

The computed t values and p-values for both autocratic and democratic leadership styles suggest that the differences in mean scores between different years in service are not statistically significant. In this case, the p-values for both autocratic and democratic leadership styles are greater than .05, which means that there is not enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in mean scores between different years in service. The computed t values and p-values for both transformational and servant leadership

styles suggest that the differences in mean scores between different years in service are not statistically significant. In this case, the p-values for both transformational and servant leadership styles are greater than .05, which means that there is not enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in mean scores between different years in service.

Table 7. Effects of the Improvement Leaderships to Leadership Styles

Factors of Leadership Improvements	Leadership Styles
Ensure clarity and visibility of goals:	Leaders who ensure clarity and visibility of goals are more likely to be effective in achieving organizational goals. This factor is particularly important for transformational and strategic leaders who seek to create a vision and motivate others towards it. A study by Joo et al. (2016) found that transformational leadership positively influences goal clarity and goal commitment. Similarly, a study by Park et al. (2018) found that strategic leadership positively influences the clarity of organizational goals.
Facilitate accountability and responsibility:	Leaders who facilitate accountability and responsibility create a culture of ownership and empowerment. This factor is particularly important for participative and servant leaders who seek to involve employees in decision-making and encourage them to take ownership of their work. A study by Oh et al. (2021) found that participative leadership positively influences accountability and responsibility, while a study by Goleman et al. (2013) found that servant leadership is associated with a higher sense of responsibility.
Create a culture of feedback:	Leaders who create a culture of feedback are more likely to have engaged and motivated employees. This factor is particularly important for democratic and participative leaders who seek to involve employees in decision-making and seek their input. A study by Kim et al. (2019) found that democratic leadership positively influences feedback-seeking behavior, while a study by Oh et al. (2021) found that participative leadership positively influences feedback giving and receiving.
Build trust and transparency:	Leaders who build trust and transparency create a culture of openness and honesty. This factor is particularly important for transformational and servant leaders who seek to inspire and empower employees. A study by Ou et al. (2015) found that transformational leadership positively influences trust and transparency, while a study by Farooq et al. (2018) found that servant leadership positively influences trust.
Focus on continuous performance management:	Leaders who focus on continuous performance management are more likely to have high-performing employees. This factor is particularly important for transactional and strategic leaders who seek to ensure that employees meet performance expectations. A study by Huang et al. (2020) found that transactional leadership positively influences performance management, while a study by

In summary, the factors of leadership improvements are closely linked to various leadership styles. Different leadership styles have varying strengths and weaknesses in relation to the different factors of leadership improvements. Therefore, it is important for leaders to adopt a flexible leadership approach that incorporates the different factors of leadership improvements and leverages the strengths of different leadership styles.

Problem 4. Based on the findings, what continuous model to leadership styles improvement can be proposed.

Diagram 1. Educational Continuous Improvement Model

Set clear expectations and provide guidance and direction to help team members grow and develop. This might involve creating new leadership training programs, developing mentoring programs for new school leaders, or establishing new communication channels to facilitate collaboration. This might involve providing ongoing support and training for school leaders, establishing accountability measures, and regularly assessing progress.

The PDCA Cycle

Plan: In this stage, the organization identifies the problem or opportunity for improvement, defines the goals and objectives, and develops a plan to achieve them. The researchers used the PDCA cycle to identify the root causes of the inefficiencies and develop a plan to address them. The researchers used the PDCA cycle to identify the quality issues, develop a plan to address them, implement the changes, and evaluate the results using sensory analysis.

Kaizen Approach

The researchers used the Kaizen approach to identify areas for improvement, involve employees in the improvement process, and implement changes. By focusing on small, incremental improvements and involving employees at all levels of the organization, organizations can create a culture of innovation and improvement that can lead to significant improvements in performance over time.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings presented, it is concluded that:

Age is a significant factor in determining the effectiveness of transformational leadership, with older leaders tending to have higher transformational leadership scores than younger leaders. Educational attainment is associated with higher mean scores in transformational leadership, and under participative leadership style, individuals with a bachelor's degree had the highest mean score. Gender is not a significant predictor of leadership style preference for autocratic and democratic leadership styles, but female participants scored higher than male participants under strategic leadership. Years of service do not have a significant impact on leadership effectiveness, except for participative leadership, which may be more compatible with younger workers. The effectiveness of leadership styles such as democratic, transformational, and servant leadership can positively impact employee engagement and job satisfaction. The study found significant improvements in leadership styles across all four types based from their perceived leadership evaluation, indicating that the leader was successful in implementing changes to their leadership practices. It is also important to note that while the results are statistically significant, the context and specific measures used to assess leadership styles should be considered when making decisions about leadership practices. Leaders who ensure clarity and visibility of goals, facilitate accountability and responsibility, create a culture of feedback, build trust and transparency, focus on continuous performance management, respect differences and promote inclusion, and foster a growth mindset are more likely to have engaged, motivated, and high-performing employees. Leaders should adopt a flexible leadership approach that leverages the strengths of different leadership styles to promote these factors and achieve organizational goals. Different leadership styles are more effective in promoting each of these factors. Transformational and strategic leaders are particularly effective in ensuring clarity and visibility of goals and building trust and transparency. Participative and servant leaders are effective in facilitating accountability and responsibility and creating a culture of ownership and empowerment. Democratic and participative leaders are effective in creating a culture of feedback and promoting inclusivity. Transactional and strategic leaders are effective in focusing on continuous performance management.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Leaders should be aware of how age can impact their leadership effectiveness and seek to continually develop their skills and knowledge. Organizations can invest in education and training programs to help leaders develop transformational leadership skills. Leaders should be aware of how gender can impact leadership style preference and work to promote diversity and inclusivity in their leadership teams. When selecting leaders for participative leadership roles, consider younger workers who may be more compatible with this style.

Organizations should prioritize promoting leadership styles that positively impact employee engagement and job satisfaction, such as democratic, transformational, and servant leadership. School leaders should regularly assess their leadership practices and make improvements to ensure they are effective. When assessing leadership practices, it's important to consider the specific measures used and the context in which they were applied. School leaders should aim to ensure clarity and visibility of goals, facilitate accountability and responsibility, create a culture of feedback, build trust and transparency, focus on continuous performance management, respect differences and promote inclusion, and foster a growth mindset to promote engaged, motivated, and high-performing employees. School leaders should adopt a flexible leadership approach that leverages the strengths of different leadership styles to promote these factors and achieve organizational goals. Leaders and organizations should continue to research and explore the nuances of different leadership styles in different contexts to continually improve their leadership practices and promote positive organizational outcomes. The proposed continuous improvement model should be used in order maintain the type of leadership that school heads are utilizing and provide clear end goal of plan towards the attainment of organization's goal and objectives.

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations, so it is necessary to carry out further research related to the topic of Leadership Styles of School Heads in Public Secondary Schools Towards Educational Continuous Improvement Model in order to improve this research and add insight to readers.

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